

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetic resources

Evaluation of rice germplasm in Bangkok

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We evaluated 198 local rices from the National Rice Seed Storage Laboratory for Genetic Resources for 36 agronomic traits. Culm number, panicle length, culm length, blade color, and grain yield varied considerably.

At Bangkok Rice Experiment Station, Bangkok, soil pH is around 4.7. Annual rainfall averages 109.58 mm; temperature averages 28 °C (33 °C maximum and 24 °C minimum).

The 1988-89 experiment was laid out in a completely randomized block design.

Range, mean, and coefficient of variation for different characters in rice germplasm collection in Thailand.

Character	Range	Mean	SD	CV (%)
Leaf length (cm)	41.4 - 84.2	65.52	7.87	12.01
Leaf width (cm)	0.5 - 2.1	1.35	0.22	16.41
Culm length (cm)	60.0 - 167.8	133.80	20.00	14.95
Ligule length (cm)	6.4 - 25.0	17.78	5.55	31.24
Culm number	2 - 19	10.25	2.98	29.04
Panicle length (cm)	21.5 - 32.8	27.46	16.16	58.86
100-grain weight (g)	2.2 - 3.6	2.96	0.25	8.52

Plants were spaced 25 × 33 cm with four 5-m-long rows/plot. RD7, KDML, 105, and KTH17 were the standard checks.

Most of the varieties screened did not differ in morphology such as blade pubescence. Ligule was white with two clefts. Stigma was yellow. Apiculus was white in most rices, but red at the apex in Sao Nueng (GS.5699) and Niaw Nak (GS.5701).

Considerable variation in culm length and panicle length was observed among varieties (see table). Genotypes with desirable characters can be used as parents in breeding programs for specific locations.

Low SD for leaf width, leaf length, culm number, and 100-grain weight indicates limited scope for selection of these characters. ■

Findings from a 28-yr seed viability experiment

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In April 1963, Peter R. Jennings and I set up a germplasm bank seed storage experiment. Seed lots of varieties Siam 29, Peta, and Chianan 8 were dried at 50 °C in a convection oven to 13, 11, 7, 5, and 3.5% wet basis initial seed moisture content. After cooling, the seed lots were embedded in liberal amounts of silica gel inside airtight 1 1/2-gallon glass jars. The equilibrium seed moisture content was maintained at about 8.5%, and the jars kept at 2 °C.

Twice a year, 500 seeds of each variety were sprouted in petri dishes in 100-seed lots to measure viability. Seeds dried to 11% moisture content have shown the least drop in viability over 28 yr (see figure). This moisture content is the average of seeds kept in IRGC's short-term storage room.

The viability reading shows

Changes in seed viability over time of controlled varieties kept at 2 °C cold storeroom.

- two dormant varieties (Siam and Peta) began with moderately low germination (60-80%), which increased markedly after dormancy expired; viability remained around 96% to early 1991.
- viability of nondormant Chianan 8 deteriorated rapidly after 8 yr; by 1990, viability was less than 5%.

The longevity pattern between the indica varieties dominant in the tropics and the sinica varieties dominant in the subtropics is striking, and little known to rice workers and seed physiologists.

These findings led IRGC staff to set up a control set of 8-10 representative varieties from major rice-growing countries in the IRGC medium-term (2 °C, 40%

relative humidity [RH]) and long-term (-10 °C, 30% RH) storerooms for periodic monitoring of seed viability, and monitoring every 5 yr for the medium-term and every 10 yr for the long-term storage. These intervals follow the longevity patterns of the control varieties.

Subtropical and temperate zone varieties stored earlier were regenerated as a batch in 1973-74, before average viability dropped to 50%. Tropical varieties were rejuvenated at later intervals.

This is the longest, continuously monitored seed storage experiment on record, but the control seed lots are now running low. ■

Genetics

Combining ability of some rice cultivars with selected cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines

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We studied the general combining ability (GCA) of 18 parents and the specific combining ability (SCA) of 45 crosses in a 15 (line) × 3 (tester) mating design: 12 varieties and 3 male fertility restorer lines used as pollen parents were crossed with 3 CMS lines.

The 63 treatments (15 lines, 3 testers, and 45 F₁s) were laid out in a completely randomized block design with three replications during 1985 wet season under irrigation. Experimental plots were three 3-m-long rows. Row and plant spacing was kept at 20 × 15 cm. Five competitive plants were randomly selected from each plot for analysis.

Male fertility restorer line IET5656 was the best general combiner for grain yield, followed by Narendra 80, IR54, Z97 A, and T26 (Table 1). Madhuri and Sattari exhibited good GCA effect for test weight. Narendra 80 and Pankaj were good general combiners for tiller number; IR54 and T26 were good for plant height. Sattari and Narendra 80 and female line IR46829 A were good general combiners for early heading.

Table 1. General combining ability for grain yield and other characters of some parental lines.^a

Parents	Plant height	Heading date	Tiller number	Test weight	Grain yield
<i>CMS female lines</i>					
V20 A	-1.54*	-0.49	0.64	-2.41**	0.28
IR46829 A	-14.48**	-2.32**	-3.78**	-2.33**	-3.75*
Z97 A	16.02**	2.82**	3.14**	-0.07	3.47**
<i>Male lines</i>					
<i>Male fertility restorer lines</i>					
IR50	3.16*	4.34**	-0.16	-2.41*	2.22**
IR54	17.12**	15.25**	4.82**	0.69	9.32**
IET5656	8.35**	8.89**	5.11**	-0.30	20.77**
<i>Non-fertility restorer varieties</i>					
Sattari	-11.90**	-15.53**	-11.77**	2.95**	-17.83**
Narendra 80	-4.20*	-3.53*	10.75**	0.57	10.73**
Pankaj	1.86	7.27**	10.29**	-0.57	-10.05**
T26	20.13**	14.25**	-2.62**	-3.47**	3.25**
Madhuri	-8.32**	-2.24	-0.16	3.26**	-8.07**

^a* and ** = significant at P.05 and P.01, respectively.

Table 2. Crosses showing specific combining ability effects for grain yield and other characters.^a

Cross	Plant height	Heading date	Tiller number	Test weight	Grain yield
V20 A/IR54	26.73**	7.03*	-5.44**	1.59	-3.60*
V20 A/Sattari	-9.73**	18.08**	-3.44*	-2.45*	-2.20
IR46829 A/Pankaj	1.73	11.29**	0.11	3.96**	-3.88**
IR46829 A/Sattari	6.21	-7.62*	2.18	-0.05	8.46**
IR46829 A/T26	-15.49**	6.49	2.70	3.82**	-3.26*
Z97 A/IR50	2.95	4.59	13.64**	0.05	-5.40**
Z97 A/IET5656	4.94	-4.96	6.10**	-4.00**	23.83**

^a* and ** = significant at P. 05 and P .01, respectively.

Only seven crosses showed high SCA effects for one or more characters (Table 2). V20 A/IR54 for tall and IR46829A/T26 for dwarf plant height; IR46829 A/Sattari for early heading; IR46829 A/Pankaj and IR46829 A/T26 for test weight; 297 A/IR50 for tiller number; and Z97 A/IET5656 for grain yield were the best specific combiners.

The parental lines 297 A and IET5656 had the highest GCA effects in their respective female and male groups for grain yield, and also produced the best SCA effect for grain yield. Crosses showing high SCA effects for plant height and tiller number involved parents of high and low GCA values; parents with high GCA values exhibited high SCA effect for earlier heading date in their crosses. Parents showing high SCA values in their crosses were low general combiners for test weight. The SCA effect was more common and pro-

nounced in crosses involving male fertility restorer lines with CMS lines.

The cross combination showing high SCA effect for grain yield also showed high SCA effect for tiller number, indicating tiller number is an important yield component. ■

Relationship of genetic variances of quantitative characters in indica rice to nitrogen level

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Genetic variance reflects the magnitude of the gene effect controlling certain characters. We studied the relationship of genetic variance of 12 characters to N